

STREAMLINED GERIATRIC AND ONCOLOGICAL EVALUATION BASED ON
IC TECHNOLOGY
FOR HOLISTIC PATIENT-ORIENTED HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT
FOR OLDER MULTIMORBID PATIENTS

HORIZON 2020 PROGRAMME – TOPIC H2020-SC1-BHC-24-2020
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D1.4: DATASET OF SELF-MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PATIENT-DRIVEN IMPROVEMENT OF INDEPENDENT LIVING

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V1.2	2022-03-07	Marije Hamaker (DIAK)	Final version with dataset links included

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the development and content of the self-management recommendations for dealing with symptoms during/after cancer treatment as well as general healthy ageing recommendations. It describes the seven steps that were undertaken to develop the self-management library, the final list of subjects and symptoms that were included, and the sources that were used to obtain this list.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

In the Grant agreement, we determined that we would establish a minimum list of 15 common symptoms that were amenable to self-management. In the end, our self-management library became longer, as we included all items in the list of 27 relevant symptoms and PROMs that are included in the symptom monitoring, as well as other common symptoms that may be burdensome to older patients with multimorbidity undergoing cancer treatment. Additionally, we added 20 more general self-care recommendations for healthy ageing and dealing with cancer or its treatment.

Justification for delay in deliverable submission

The objectives related to this deliverable have been achieved on time and as scheduled in Annexe 1 (Description of the Action Part A) of the Grant Agreement N°945218.

1. Introduction

1.1. GERONTE and its objectives

GERONTE is a 5-year research and innovation project (April 2021 to Mars 2026) funded by the European Union within the framework of the H2020 Research and Innovation programme, in response to the health societal challenge topic SC1-BHC-24-2020 “Healthcare interventions for the management of the elderly multimorbid patient”. The overall aim of GERONTE is to improve quality of life - defined as well-being on three levels: global health status, physical functioning and social functioning- for older multimorbid patients, while reducing overall costs of care. To this end, GERONTE will co-design, test, and prepare for deployment an innovative cost-effective patient-centred holistic health management system, hereafter referred to as the GERONTE intervention. GERONTE intervention will rely on an ICT based application for real-time collection and integration of standardised clinical and home patient-reported data. GERONTE intervention will be demonstrated in the context of care of multimorbid patients having cancer as a dominant morbidity, and be adaptable to any other combination of morbidities.

Objectives

O1: INFORMATION gather the stakeholders and data needed for patient-centred and multi-actor complex decision-making process and management

O2: TOOLS develop ICT tools for the GERONTE intervention to be implemented

O3: METHODS develop socio-economic methods for evaluating the impacts of the implementation of the GERONTE intervention

O4: DEMONSTRATION demonstrate in 16 study sites from three EU countries the feasibility and effectiveness of the GERONTE intervention

O5: REPLICATION develop recommendations for the replication of GERONTE best practices in all European health systems

O6: ENGAGEMENT engage all stakeholders by co-designing the GERONTE intervention

1.2. Rationale

Deliverable D1.4 is part of work-package WP1 which supports GERONTE objective O1: INFORMATION. Patient empowerment by supporting self-management is an important component of the Geronte care pathway. As patients will be monitoring themselves at home, to register side-effects of treatment, decompensation of comorbidities and signs of functional decline, they will also be faced with questions about how to deal with the issues that they are having. While one important component of the care pathway is early signalling of complications to allow for early intervention by health care professionals, there is also a lot that patients can do for themselves at home to enhance their life-style, decrease burden of signs and symptoms or to improve outcomes.

This deliverable reports on the method of obtaining the self-management recommendations. The library of self-management recommendations, GERDAT005, can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334779>.

2. Method

2.1. Determining which subjects to provide recommendations for

Selection of signs and symptoms for which to provide self-management recommendations was based on several factors

- Symptoms selected for home monitoring (see deliverable 1.2)
- Commonly occurring signs and symptoms of cancer or in relation to cancer-treatment, based on validated questionnaires for assessing symptom burden and quality of life (see deliverable 1.2)
- General healthy ageing recommendations encountered during online search
- Supplemented with additional subjects encountered during literature and online searches

2.2. Literature search

As a first step, a literature review was undertaken on MEDLINE and EMBASE to determine if any previous scientific publications were available that could serve as a library for the self-management recommendations.

The following search was performed on January 14th 2021: self[tiab] AND (care[tiab] OR management[tiab] OR monitoring[tiab] OR efficacy[tiab]) AND (older[tiab] OR geriatric[tiab] OR multimorb*[tiab]) AND (cancer[tiab] OR oncology[tiab] OR malign*[tiab]). Searches were limited to 2000 onward.

This yielded 1058 hits in pubmed and 1766 hits in Embase. While this search retrieved several studies on home-monitoring applications, none provided a complete library with self-management recommendations.

2.3. Local sources

As the second step, patient information leaflets and booklets available at the Diakonessenhuis Utrecht, the Netherlands, and the Catholic University Leuven, Belgium were consulted to retrieve recommendations already provided to patients undergoing cancer treatment at the moment.

This yielded input on the following subjects:

- UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
 - Diarrhoea, vomiting, nausea, poor appetite, pain, fever/feeling ill, fatigue, feeling depressed/irritable, feeling worried/nervous/uncertain, sore/dry mouth, tingling, rash/skin issue, constipation, hair loss, teary eyes, sexuality and intimacy, muscle/joint pain, change in taste/smell
- Diakonessenhuis patient leaflets
 - Hair loss, change of skin, burning eyes, change in smell/taste, sore/dry mouth, fatigue, intimacy and sexuality, bleeding and bruising, urinary symptoms, trouble sleeping, wound problems, ostomy issues, incontinence, faecal incontinence.

2.4. Online search

As the third step, an online search was performed in google using search terms “health ageing”. In addition, three cancer information websites were consulted.

- Kwf.nl
- Kanker.nl
- wcrf.org

For any remaining topics that were identified for which no sources for recommendations had thus far been retrieved, specific online searches were performed to identify any available information.

2.5. Expert opinion

As the fourth step, for any topics still without recommendations, expert opinion was sought from advance practice nurses, (para)medical experts and/or other health care professionals with expertise pertaining to the subject.

2.6. Expert review

As the final step, all recommendations were gathered in one document which was subsequently reviewed by five medical specialists (3 geriatricians, 2 oncologists) and three advance practice nurses to achieve consensus on the content of the self-management library. Any disagreement was resolved through a consensus discussion. The final document was approved by all eight reviewers.

2.7. Translation

Once the English version of the document was agreed upon, it was translated to both Dutch and French to allow for inclusion in the patient applications.

3. Conclusion

This document reports on the process of developing the self-management recommendation library for patients undergoing cancer treatment and optimizing healthy life-style. A full overview of the included subjects and symptoms, as well as the sources from which the self-management recommendations were retrieved can be found in Annexe 1. The full self-management recommendation library, GERDAT005, can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334779>.

Annexe 1:

Overview of signs and symptoms for which recommendations have been made available in the self-management library, and the sources from which recommendations were collected. The actual recommendations, GERDAT005, can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334779>.

1a. Topics on general recommendations for healthy ageing and health lifestyle

	Topic	Source
1	FLUID INTAKE	ageuk.org.uk
2	ALCOHOL	British Geriatric Society healthy ageing
3	HEALTHY DIET	ageuk.org.uk fda.gov www.voedingenkankerinfo.nl
4	ADJUST DIET	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment www.voedingenkankerinfo.nl
5	SMOKING	ageuk.org.uk
6	ORAL HYGIENE	ageuk.org.uk
7	MEDICATION SAFETY	fda.gov
8	MEDICATION FOR SYMPTOMS	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
9	EXERCISE	ageuk.org.uk
10	FALLS PREVENTION	Beteroud.nl
11	FEET	ageuk.org.uk
12	MENTAL ACTIVITY	Mayo clinic
13	SLEEP	ageuk.org.uk Trimbos instituut Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet: adviezen om beter te slapen
14	REST AND ACTIVITY	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
15	ENERGY	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
16	SOCIAL	ageuk.org.uk Trimbos instituut
17	LONELINESS	loketgezondleven.nl (from the Dutch ministry of Health)
18	GRATITUDE	Trimbos instituut
19	URINATION	Diakonessenhuis patient information
20	DEFECATION	Diakonessenhuis patient information

1b. Topics of recommendations related to symptoms in the daily/weekly/monthly symptom reporting checklists

1	DYSPNOEA	KWF patient booklet/leaflet: als de dood nabij is
2	DIARRHOEA	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
3	VOMITING	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
4	NAUSEA	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
5	DAILY ACTIVITIES LIMITED BY BOWEL/URINARY PROBLEMS	Diakonessenhuis patient booklets/leaflets Incontinence/Fecal incontinence
6	POOR APPETITE	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
7	UNINTENTIONAL WEIGHT LOSS	World Cancer Research Fund: Tijdens kanker, goed eten en omgaan met klachten
8	UNINTENTIONAL WEIGHT GAIN	World Cancer Research Fund: Tijdens kanker, goed eten en omgaan met klachten

1b. Topics of recommendations related to symptoms in the daily/weekly/monthly symptom reporting checklists

1	DYSPNOEA	KWF patient booklet/leaflet: als de dood nabij is
2	DIARRHOEA	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
3	VOMITING	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
4	NAUSEA	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
5	DAILY ACTIVITIES LIMITED BY BOWEL/URINARY PROBLEMS	Diakonessenhuis patient booklets/leaflets Incontinence/Fecal incontinence
6	POOR APPETITE	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
7	UNINTENTIONAL WEIGHT LOSS	World Cancer Research Fund: Tijdens kanker, goed eten en omgaan met klachten
8	UNINTENTIONAL WEIGHT GAIN	World Cancer Research Fund: Tijdens kanker, goed eten en omgaan met klachten
9	PAIN	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment KWF patient booklet/leaflet: Pijn bij kanker
10	FEVER/FEELING ILL	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
11	FATIGUE	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet Chemotherapie op het DBOH
12	TROUBLE SLEEPING	Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet: adviezen om beter te slapen
13	TROUBLE REMEMBERING/ THINKING; CONFUSION	KWF patient booklet/leaflet: Ouderen en kanker No sources found, expert opinion/consortium partners
14	FEELING DEPRESSED OR IRRITABLE	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
15	FEELING NERVOUS, WORRIED OR UNCERTAIN	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
16	CHANGE IN MOBILITY	No sources found, expert opinion/consortium partners
17	UNSTEADY ON YOUR FEEL/FALLS	No sources found, expert opinion/consortium partners
18	FORCED TO SPEND TIME IN BED	No sources found, expert opinion/consortium partners
19	NEED HELP WITH DAILY ACTIVITIES	No sources found, expert opinion/consortium partners
20	SORE/DRY MOUTH	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet Chemotherapie op het DBOH
21	TINGLING HAND/FEET	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
22	RASH/SKIN ISSUES	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet Chemotherapie op het DBOH
23	WOUND PROBLEMS	Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflets Naar huis na een darmoperatie/ borstamputatie/borstsparende operatie
24	BLOODY STOOLS OR MUCUS	No sources found, expert opinion/consortium partners
25	OSTOMY ISSUES	Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet: Darmstoma
26	COUGH	No sources found, expert opinion/consortium partners
27	COUGH UP BLOOD	No sources found, expert opinion/consortium partners

1c. Topics of recommendations for other common issues related to cancer, its treatment or their sequelae

1	CONSTIPATION	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
2	SEXUALITY AND INTIMACY	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet Chemotherapie op het DBOH Kanker.nl
3	HAIR LOSS	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet Chemotherapie op het DBOH
4	DRY, BURNING OR TEARY EYES	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet Chemotherapie op het DBOH
5	MUSCLE OR JOINT PAIN	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment
6	CHANGES IN TASTE OR SMELL	UZ Leuven guidelines concerning your chemotherapy treatment Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet Chemotherapie op het DBOH
7	URINARY PROBLEMS	Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet Chemotherapie op het DBOH
8	BLEEDING OR BRUISING	Diakonessenhuis patient booklet/leaflet Chemotherapie op het DBOH

1d. Sources used for recommendations regarding communication and how to prepare for your next consultations

- www.rijnstate.nl/tips
- KWF patient booklet/leaflet: kanker, in gesprek met je arts
- www.kanker.nl/sites/default/files/library_files/Studie%203%20Gespekswijzer%20start%20pdf.pdf
- Literature review prepared for Geronte to address this topic:

Hamaker ME, van Walree IC, Seghers PAL (Nelleke), van den Bos F, Soubeyran P, O’Hanlon S, Rostoft. S. **Information needs of older patients newly diagnosed with cancer.** J Geriatr Oncol 2021 Sep 23;S1879-4068(21)00212-5. doi: 10.1016/j.jgo.2021.09.011.

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